

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369236331>

Insights on multiphase treatment towards modeling the fluid dynamics of gas-stirred baths

Conference Paper · December 2022

CITATIONS

0

READS

111

2 authors:

Rishikesh Mishra

Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur

13 PUBLICATIONS 51 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Dipak Mazumdar

Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra

135 PUBLICATIONS 3,346 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Insights on multiphase treatment towards modeling the fluid dynamics of gas-stirred baths

Rishikesh Mishra* and Dipak Mazumdar

Department of Materials Science and Engineering, IIT Kanpur, IN 208016

*Corresponding author's email: mrishi@iitk.ac.in

Abstract

Over the past five decades, computational fluid dynamic (CFD) modelling of gas-stirred baths has come a long way, from quasi-single phase approaches to sophisticated multiphase treatments such as interface capturing, population balance, discrete particle mapping, and coalescence-breakup dynamics. Through analysis of new and existing results, both physical and numerical, we examine the underlying concepts which can guide the development of realistic models. Towards this, we examine the critical factors required to correctly configure the superficially different, but practically equivalent, Eulerian and Lagrangian treatments of the dispersed phase, as well as the important but under-examined role of sharp interface treatment in volume of fluid (VOF) based modelling of large continuous interfaces. These collectively illustrate the role of qualitative inferences in underscoring the tendencies of an approximate model vis-à-vis the actual system, so as to improve both realism and robustness, an aspect which tends to be lost if one overemphasizes gross quantification through slag eye or mixing time.

1. INTRODUCTION

As we see rapid progress and incorporation of advanced CFD strategies in the multiphase modelling of gas-stirred systems, it becomes important to consider the underlying concepts to guide the search for meaningful results. We look at two popular components used in present day multiphase modelling of such systems, the underlying factors to be considered, and the impact of such considerations.

2. EQUIVALENCE, UNCERTAINTY AND IMPORTANCE OF DISPERSED PHASE TREATMENTS

Two prominent schools of modeling the behaviour of injected gas phase, along with their advantages and disadvantages, are:

Lagrangian	Eulerian
o detailed implementation of interactions made per particle	o interactions are defined through statistical parameters (kernels) for the population
+ computationally inexpensive, ODE based	-- computationally expensive due to increase in momentum PDEs
-- discrete mass treatment puts theoretical limits on void fractions	+ symmetric treatment of phases potentially allows for better dispersed-continuum transition

Within steelmaking literature, the most elaborate eulerian multi-fluid treatment has involved coupling an eulerian dispersed phase with a VOF based second phase, which makes it practically identical to the lagrangian method [1]. If we consider a proper multifluid eulerian system, i.e. one capable of handling both dispersed and continuum limits of constituent phases, it is evident that the quality of its solution is sensitive to strategies of sharpness preservation and dispersed-continuum switching. Subject to their effectiveness for a given case, benchmark results show performance comparable to shared-momentum VOF methods [2]. Fig. 1 shows the solution obtained with a representative state-of-the-art eulerian multi-fluid formulation [2] built with the libraries of OpenFOAM-9. There, a tradeoff is apparent between dispersed transport capability and sharpness preservation. This calls for further investigation

when blending the two regimes, which indeed appears to be the focus of studies towards extending the framework in this direction. Presented alongside these results is a comparable simulation performed with a lagrangian dispersed phase model (DPM) coupled to a mixture VOF model. The major argument made in favour of the eulerian dispersed phase approach over the lagrangian DPM is the low void fraction limit on discrete phase occupancy for the latter. While this is a valid argument, it needs to be noted that in their present form, the eulerian approach also needs special treatment to handle higher gas fraction. This fact, combined with the apparent sharpness trade-off currently seen in the eulerian setup, and its overall computational overhead, is yet to justify its adoption as a superior alternative.

Fig. 1. Qualitatively comparable solutions obtained with a DPM-VOF coupled solver (left), algebraically blended scale-adapting Euler-Euler multi-fluid solver with interface compression to improve interface sharpness (middle) and without interface compression to improve dispersed phase modeling (right)

For handling higher gas fraction within studies applying the lagrangian framework to steelmaking studies, two approaches have recently been forwarded, although neither of these addresses the implications of dispersed phase fraction on local mass. The first of these proposals adopts a transition to VOF at critical void fraction[3], similar to blending of dispersed and continuum regimes in the eulerian formulation. This needs careful consideration since bubbles in experiments tend to maintain equilibrium separation and maintain their size distribution upto critical loading ratios, which calls to consider eddy interactions and collision models on top of void fraction based conditions. The other proposal redistributes the lagrangian point sources using a distance based interpolation [4].

While neither study touches upon this, a correct mapping of bubble volume must ensure mass conservation and volume fraction boundedness. Attempting such an exercise promptly reveals that such a mapping needs to consider the global distribution of dispersed phase properties such as voidage, dispersed phase mass and velocity, thereby transitioning essentially to an eulerian strategy. Indeed, such a framework, consisting of a global distribution and transport of such population statistics, forms the eulerian dispersed phase method of moments [5]. In summary, we can see a general convergence of these seemingly different approaches, which may therefore be compared based on accuracy of induced flow profile, and computational expense.

Irrespective of the approach adopted, if one is interested in additionally capturing the internal dynamics of the plume, additional closure for interactions such as force and collision need to be supplied. The drag force is pivotal in defining these interactions. Other exchanges primarily introduce variations in bubble trajectories about this mean, rather than affect the achieved slip velocity. These secondary interactions include Turbulent Dispersion (TD) which is captured as an additional drag force, and mechanisms such as lateral lift force or virtual mass which describe complex auto-correlations of acceleration.

It is worth noting that there is considerable overlap between these different ways of describing the self-coupled state of momentum within the plume and consequently, a considerable overlap in the system's behaviour under their influence. Furthermore, differences in implementation across CFD codes can lead to starkly different manifestations of the plume under the influence of the same interaction. For example, while derived from similar prescriptions, the TD model adopted by ANSYS FluentTM predicts a much

higher dispersion compared to the corresponding model implemented in OpenFOAM, even if the latter is modified to follow the implementation prescribed by the former's Theory Manual [6]. Similarly, OpenFOAM implementations show significantly more effect of the lift force, as compared to Fluent, whose plume behaviour is dominated by TD. Evidence of such sensitivity to implementation has also been observed elsewhere [7]. This seems indicative of such behaviour found in heuristic strategies which are added atop well-established numerical methods to solve complex problems. This makes it important to consider the prescriptions regarding the relative importance of forces with some skepticism, as some of these may be manifestations of numerical biases introduced by a specific implementation, rather than tendencies of the physical system it attempts to mimic.

In addition to the interplay of forces in determining the plume's shape, its internal dynamics are also subject to bubble shape and size distribution. This adds an additional, implicit uncertainty due to unpredictable initial configuration. As seen in Fig. 2, it is experimentally evident that the exact population dynamics are sensitive to the injector size and porosity, atleast at low flow rates (such as during rinsing). As a result, the initial bubble population cannot be modelled exactly, as injectors are likely to vary individually as well as through their lifecycle, e.g. due to clogging.

Fig. 2. Gas plume behaviour at flow rate of 3 NLPM (0.0068 W/kg) injected through a 0.25 in. nozzle (left), 0.25 in. porous plug (middle), and 1 in. porous plug (right)

However, in the aforementioned studies using the lagrangian approach [3,4], even a partial implementation of these approaches is able to generate reasonable flow profiles, without breaking the stability of the numerical system. This indicates a minor influence of such strategies on the overall domain of analysis. This is likely due to the small gas phase density, which wields a small influence on local mass in the system even at considerable void fractions. Such minor influence also seems to corroborate the analysis presented in Mazumdar and Guthrie (2010) where the gross kinetic energy of recirculation is found to be proportional largely to the overall buoyant energy input into the system [8].

3. ROLE OF SHARP INTERFACE TREATMENT USED IN VOF BASED MODELS

The choice of interface capturing strategy has a significant impact on the underlying flow field, to the extent that a heavily distorted and unrealistic solution may be generated by an inadequate VOF strategy applied to a given problem, such as the solutions demonstrated in Fig. 1. Among the two prominent classes, much remains to be understood about commercially implemented geometric VOF methods, especially their extension to more than two phases, as well as their suitability to scale-adaptive Euler-Euler multi-fluid VOF models. In comparison, the algebraic class of methods is straightforward to implement, using higher order interpolation to preserve the sharpness of the interface during advection.

Fig. 3 shows some variations of flow profile generated by different grid and equation discretizations, subject to the same set of governing equations (standard k- ϵ based shared momentum incompressible VOF-DPM system). There, it is evident that under an inadequate configuration, severe distortion of flow

can occur. This is due to the interaction of near-wall turbulence and the sensitivity of the interface strategy to deal with perturbations thus induced. Flow profiles such as the one obtained with poor numerics can be widely seen in contemporary CFD investigations of gas-stirred ladles. Such an incorrect flow profile has direct implications on the overall energy input into the system [9] and affects any subsequent models interacting with this flow profile. Significant improvement can be seen with an appropriate strategy, without resorting to LES, whose value addition may then be evaluated without undue misattribution.

Fig. 3: A representative selection of flow field obtained through various discretization procedures, where viable candidate strategies are seen to approach experimental profile with grid refinement.

4. CONCLUSION

The role of dispersed phase modeling is largely restricted within the plume, wherein there lies considerable uncertainty and sensitivity to alternative implementations of sophisticated models. In contrast, the choice of well-crafted interface capturing procedure has a profound impact on the developed flow field.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhu, B., Zhang, B. & Chattopadhyay, K., Numerical Simulation of Fluid Flow in a Gas-Stirred Ladle Using a Particle-Free Surface Coupled Model. *Metall Mater Trans B* **51**, (2020), pp. 898–905
- [2] Meller, R., Schlegel, F. and Lucas, D., Basic Verification of a Numerical Framework Applied to a Morphology Adaptive Multifield Two-fluid Model Considering Bubble Motions. *Intl. J Num Meth Flu*, **93**(3), (2021), pp.748-773
- [3] Liu, Y., Ersson, M., Liu, H., Jönsson, P., & Gan, Y., Comparison of Euler-Euler Approach and Euler-Lagrange Approach to Model Gas Injection in a Ladle. *Steel Res Intl*, **90**(5), (2019), 1800494
- [4] Haas, T., Schubert, C., Eickhoff, M., & Pfeifer, H., Full-Scale Large Eddy Simulation of a 185 t Ladle Optimizing a Hybrid Eulerian Grid and a Discrete Bubble Mapping Approach. *Steel Res Int*, **93**(6), (2022), 2100653
- [5] Heylmun J.C., Kong B., Passalacqua A., Fox R., A Quadrature-based Moment Method for Polydisperse Bubbly Flows, *Comp Phys Comm*, **244**, (2019),Pages 187-204
- [6] ANSYS Fluent Theory Guide 12.1, Section 15.2.2
- [7] Mathur, A., & He, S., Performance and implementation of the Launder–Sharma low-Reynolds number turbulence model. *Comp & Flu*, **79**, 2013, pp.134-139
- [8] Mazumdar, D., & Guthrie, R. I., Modeling energy dissipation in slag-covered steel baths in steelmaking ladles. *Metall Mater Trans B*, **41**(5), (2010), pp.976-989
- [9] Mishra, R., & Mazumdar, D., An Assessment of Numerical Approaches Toward Multi-Phase Hydrodynamic Modelling of Inert Gas Stirred Ladle Systems, *Proc. Steelsim* (2019), Toronto. pp.758-768